

An Optimal Feature Selection with Ensemble Based Classification of Sentiments Using Forest Optimization Algorithm for Product Review

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Abstract :

Feature subset selection is a method to select a set of relevant features from a high dimensionality dataset to optimize the performance of classifiers. The meaningful words extracted from data, forms a set of features for Sentiment Analysis (SA). The various evolutionary algorithms, like Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Genetic Algorithm (GA), have been applied to subset for feature selection problem and computational can still be improved. This paper presents a result to feature subset selection problem for classification of Sentiment Analysis by means of ensemble-based classifiers. It involves of a hybrid technique of Forest Optimization Algorithm (FOA) and Maximum Relevance and minimum redundancy and (MRmr) based feature selection. Ensemble-based classification is implemented to improve the results of individual classifiers. The Forest Optimization Algorithm as a feature selection technique has been applied to many classification datasets. The classifiers used for ensemble methods for are the Naïve Bayes (NB) and k-Nearest Neighbor (k-NN). The outcomes are further enhanced by ensemble of k-NN, NB, and Support Vector Machine (SVM) with more accuracy.

Keywords : Classification, data mining, evolutionary algorithms, ensemble, sentiment analysis, feature subset selection

1. Introduction :

Classification of sentiments is essentially a method to determine the separation of a given sentence, document and text. Sentiment analysis and classification use both machine learning and natural language processing (NLP) techniques. Nowadays, the Internet is using social media as a consistent source of information on a day-to-day basis. The Social websites play a vital source of information. People share their thoughts about almost everything, e.g., product review social or political issues, book, movie any product, book, movie, social etc., on these websites. Generally, these reviews are in the text form. Openly shared reviews done in blogs or articles are used to detect the common customer opinion for any products [1]. The most important issue that arises while collecting the data from social networking sites is that the reviews mostly contain spelling and /or grammatical mistakes and data is typically so large that correcting those mistakes is humanly is not possible. Whenever the data is being mined from any of the social network, it has large parts of unwanted information, including html tags, as compared to actual meaningful and useful information comprising of review text. There are various pre-processing techniques to apply on the mined data first and then it is studied. To get high dimensional data feature subset selection (FSS) is used as a pre-processing technique in data mining. In the case of social network mining, it is usual for the data to be studied to have higher dimensions. Classification of such data with sensible computational cost has become a significant area of research in recent years. Most of the results proposed for sentiment analysis are either based on dataset pre-processing techniques or classifier to improve classification accuracy. Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Genetic Algorithm (GA) have been used for feature subset selection from the Artificial Intelligence domain. The PSO- and GA-based results have to improve classification accuracy but these solutions are computationally expensive, so the overall performance has been affected. PSO and GA are meta-heuristic algorithms that use population of initial solutions. They are used for optimization problems. This research presents an ensemble based classification of sentiments using an evolutionary algorithm, named the *Forest Optimization Algorithm* (FOA) and proposed in [2]. The seeding procedure of trees is

simulated in this algorithm. It is inspired by some trees that outlive other trees based on their better survival conditions. FOA produces a best tree (subset of features) among all other trees based on performance. FOA has outperformed PSO and GA when applied to target functions and an optimization problem of feature weighting using continuous weights [2].

2. Literature Review :

Feature selection supports to decrease the number of attributes to be stored in database to get clear of unrelated or superfluous features to produce more useful and efficient results. Feature subset selection algorithms are either categorized as Wrapper and Filter approaches or as comprehensive search, heuristic search, meta-heuristic search methods, and methods based on artificial neural networks (ANN) [3]. There are two approaches for feature selection; the filter approach was one of the initial techniques used for feature subset selection. The filter approach makes use of characteristics and statistics of data instead of learning algorithms. Mostly, it performs two methods of ranking the variables by evaluating the importance of them and subset selection of feature [4]. The second approach is the Wrapper approach that makes use of learning algorithms while searching for a suitable feature subset. The chosen classifier is a part of feature selection procedure; wrapper method makes good feature selection by considering the classification accuracy as a part of its evaluation function [4]. Wrapper methods, when compared to filter methods, are more time consuming for datasets with large numbers of features. On the other hand, they do produce better results and are more accurate than filter methods. There many are researchers who have tried to solve sentiments analysis by using different techniques from machine learning domain and by using ensemble-based classification techniques [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12]. In [7], authors present the use of sentiment analysis as a technique for analyzing the presence of human handling in companion ads drawn from the open website. Traditional techniques have not focused on sentiment as a textual cue of human handling and as a replacement for other visual signs (e.g., the existence of tattoos in linked images), or textual signs (specific styles of keywords; ad-writing, etc.). They applied two broadly quoted sentiment analysis models: the Stanford models and Netflix, and also train binary and categorical (multiclass) sentiment models using companion review data crawled from the open web. The individual model performances and

exploratory analysis motivated them to construct two ensemble sentiment models that correctly serve as a feature proxy to identify human handling. In [11], authors discover the properties of feature selection on sentiment analysis of Chinese online reviews. Initially, N-POS-grams and N-char-grams are selected as the potential sentimental features. Then, the enhanced Document Frequency method is used to select feature subsets, and the Boolean Weighting method is implemented to analyze feature weight. The chi-square test is carried out to test the significance of investigational results. The results suggest that sentiment analysis of Chinese online reviews obtains higher accuracy when taking 4-POS-grams as features. Additionally, the enhanced document frequency accomplishes significant improvement in sentiment analysis of Chinese online reviews.

The MRmR (Maximum Relevance and minimum Redundancy)-based [13] feature selection method first focuses on the correlation among the features. The features must not be highly correlated to each other as it may root redundancy. Then, the significance of features with the class label is reserved into explanation. Mutual information (MI) is the way to measure the level of similarity or simply the redundancy between features. To measure the maximum relevance of features with respect to the class again we use mutual information. We need MI for the relevance measure to be maximized and MI for the redundancy measure to be minimized [14]. Two methods are designed to combine the redundancy and relevance of features in one function: (1) MID: Mutual Information Difference criterion and (2) MIQ: Mutual Information Quotient criterion. The divisive combination of redundancy and relevance, i.e., MIQ has outperformed the other difference method in the case of discrete data [14]. They have applied these MRmR criteria for gene selection task.

Sentiment classification is basically a task of opinion mining used to extract people's unanimous reviews about any topic, event, or product [1]. Sentiment analysis or opinion mining is a step-wise procedure to give the results of this classification task. Usually this classification is binary, either the reviews are negative or positive about the corresponding topic, event, or product. Mostly, sentiment analysis (SA) and opinion mining (OM) are interchangeable but Walaa Medhat in 2014 defined them with slight differentiation [15].

Genetic algorithm has been applied to feature selection problem with changed variations and hybridization with other algorithms / methods, effectively over the years. Ahmed Abbasi, Hsinchun Chen, and Arab Salem used GA to select a features-based information gain technique and then used those features for sentiment classification of English and Arabic text [18]. A hybrid method was proposed which uses an ensemble of GA and Naïve Bayes for sentiment classification [17]. It has improved the accuracy of movie review dataset to 93.80%. Kalaivani used hybrid of information gain based genetic algorithm with bagging technique for feature selection for opinion mining. This GA based hybrid method has shown high accuracy of 87.50% when applied to movie review dataset [16]. The Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm has been applied to the problem of feature selection for sentiment analysis in recent years. Most classifiers have combined this algorithm with other existing machine learning classifying techniques and have succeeded to achieve better classification accuracy. Bernali Sahu and Debahuti Mishra [19] presented a novel feature selection algorithm based on PSO for cancer micro array data. This novel algorithm for feature selection outperformed K-NN, SVM, and PNN (Probabilistic Neural Network) [19]. There are approaches based on deep learning for the sentiment analysis problem. The results are comparable with other techniques but computational cost is comparatively high as compared to conventional approaches [20].

A hybrid of PSO-SVM was presented by Basari et al. in 2013; this hybrid method helped improve the sentiment classification accuracy from 71.87% to 77% for the IMDB movie review dataset [21]. In 2014 another hybrid approach of PSO and ACO (Ant Colony Optimization) was proposed for web-based opinion mining by George Stylios. This bio-inspired method achieved 90.59% accuracy using 10 fold cross validation approach while outperforming the C4.5 algorithm with 83.66% accuracy [1]. In 2014 PSO was also used to select features for thermal face recognition and results showed a success rate of 90.28% for all images [22]. Lin Shang et al. has used binary version of PSO after modifying the basic algorithm into sentiment classification oriented approach and applied it to customer review datasets. The results have shown that this is superior to the basic binary PSO-based feature selection algorithm [23]. Ensemble-based classifiers are called multi-classifier systems (MCS). MCS give better results than implementing individual classifiers alone [24]. The basic topologies to design MCS are explored below.

2.1 Conditional Topology :

This topology typically works with one classifier selected as a primary classifier out of all the available classifiers in an ensemble or a multi-classifier system. If the first classifier fails to properly classify the input data it takes the second classifier. The choice of the next classifier can either be dynamic or static. One example of dynamic selection can be decision trees. The method of classification can stay until the data is correctly classified or if all the classifiers have been used. MCS can be computationally effective if the primary classifier is efficient. One way to keep it computationally efficient is to keep the heavy classifiers at the end of the queue of available classifiers [25].

2.2 Hierarchical (Serial) Topology :

Hierarchical topology of classifiers help narrow down the most accurate classification as the data passes through the classifiers. The classifiers are used in succession where, with each classifier, the error of classification gets minimized or the result gets more focused on the actual class of data. The classifier with minimum error should be the successor here. Although, the correct classification must be ensured after every classifier, otherwise, the next classifier will not be able to correctly classify the input data [25].

2.3 Hybrid Topology :

As some classifiers perform better on certain types of datasets, thus, the hybrid topology basically selects the best classifier for the type of input data [25]. To select the best classifiers different type of classifiers are implemented in this multi-classifier mechanism or an ensemble.

2.4 Multiple (Parallel) Topology :

Parallel or multiple topology based system of multi-classifiers is the most commonly used. In this system, all the classifiers operate in parallel on the input data. The result of each classifier is integrated in one place or function, and then the final classification is chosen according to the implemented design logic to select the appropriate classifier for the data type [25].

3. Proposed Methodology :

The feature subset selection process is performed by Forest Optimization Algorithm and pre-processing of features or attributes has been done by MRmR technique. The MRmR technique always eliminates inappropriate and redundant features before applying the feature subset selection module. The flow chart of the proposed methodology is given in Figure 1. The proposed approach combines MRmR- and FOA-based feature subset selection to complete effectual and improved solutions. The proposed approach flow is shown here:

Figure 1 : Flowchart of MRmR-based FOA.

3.1 Process 1 : Preprocessing of sentiment analysis datasets:

Dataset :

The dataset for sentiment analysis we have used for this classification task is taken from Amazon and constructed by John Blitzer and Mark Dredze [26]. This dataset contains diverse kinds of products and their reviews, including books, Kitchen appliances, electronics, and DVDs. All reviews are in underdone form with

html tags of review id, review text, date, title, rating, product, and user location. Product reviews with five stars rating. Star rating reviews are converted to positive reviews if they have more than three stars or negative if they have less than three stars, and the rest of the reviews have been discarded because of their unclear polarity. We have used book review and electronic datasets for the classification task. To evaluate these reviews, preprocessing was required. Following are the preprocessing steps that have been applied:

- Label, Review id and review text were extracted from html tags. Review text is the basic text. It is considered for analysis.
- The basic text was converted to lower case and punctuation symbol were removed.
- Stop words were not considered for analysis. Hence it is removed. Alphanumeric characters were removed.
- Stemming was applied by using Porter Stemmer method [27].
- Length of word less than three letters was also removed.

The input to algorithm must be in a form of feature vector. After preprocessing, we get the bag of words (BOW). This BOW basically forms our feature vector.

3.2 Process 2 : MRmR- and Forest Optimization Algorithm-Based Feature Subset Selection :

The bag-of-words (BOW) or feature vector that we have created in process 1 is very large and still it contains many redundant features. The redundant and irrelevant features disturb the classification accuracy and the larger size of feature vector increases the time of computation. To avoid this, we need to perform feature subset selection methods on this feature vector to achieve a more useful and efficient set of features.

3.2.1 MRmR Feature Subset Selection :

MRmR (Maximum Relevance and minimum Redundancy) is used to decrease the size of feature vector [5]. The subset of features obtained through

MRmR is effectual and produces more precise results. Experiments and Results have shown that the MIQ (Mutual Information Quotient) criterion is more suitable to use with discrete data out of the two MRmR criteria. The set of features obtained by using MIQ, are forwarded to Forest Optimization Algorithm to obtain the best subset of features. This subset of features will give the highest classification accuracy.

Maximal Relevance and Minimal Redundancy (MRmR) is based on the mutual information that measures the amount of information shared between two features. The mutual information between two variables X and Y is defined as the joint probability distribution of the two variables X and Y .

The mutual information of a feature and a class is mentioned as Relevance of the feature with the class. The mutual information of a feature with other features is mentioned as redundancy of the feature. MRmR for any feature k is expressed as follows:

$$\text{MRmR } k = \text{Relevance } k - \text{Redundancy } k$$

This measure of MRmR emphasizes that low redundancy and high relevance describes the feature is mutually exclusive to each other features and extremely dependent on the class [5].

3.2.2 Forest Optimization Algorithm :

Forest Optimization Algorithm (FOA) has been used for feature subset selection. It is stimulated by the seeding method of trees in a forest [2]. There are trees in forest that live up to eras and some only live for a limited period of time. A tree's survival depends on the conditions in the area in which they have been planted. FOA pretends natural seed dispersion method, which are basically of two kinds, global and local seed distribution processes. In the local seed distribution, the seeds fall under the trees and start to grow, but in global seed distribution seeds were carried away to places that are far-away through animals, winds, or flowing water. Local seed distribution is referred as "local seeding" and global seed distribution as "global seeding" in FOA.

The original population of trees is a matrix in where each row represents a probable solution and known as a “tree”. The dimension of one tree is $1 \times N$ var. Keeping track of individual tree’s age makes it $1 \times (Nvar + 1)$ dimensional vector. The feature vector is $(N + 1)$ dimensional.

The steps involved in the Forest Optimization Algorithm are given below.

3.2.3 Trees Initialization :

Initial population of trees is arbitrarily made with age 0. The age limit of trees is the predefined parameter “Lifetime” for each tree. When any tree outgrows the age limit it will be lost from the candidate tree population. The first variable of each tree represents its age and other variables are the features of a solution vector. Primarily all features are present in the vector. Feature presence is represented by 1 and absence by 0 in Table 1.

Table 1 : Tree encoding

Age	V_1	V_2	...	V_{Nvar}
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Local Seeding :

The function of local seeding is only applied to the newly produced trees with age 0 as shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3. The value of local seeding operator is also a predefined parameter here called “Local seeding changes (LSC)”. This LSC operator tells how many new trees will be generated in result of applying local seeding function on each tree. Random numbers equal to LSC are generated within the range of 1 to N var. If $LSC = 2$, we have $N = 4$, and random numbers are 2 and 3, then the values of feature number 2 and 3 are changed to form the new neighboring tree. This is repeated LSC number of times on each tree. Initially local seeding will be applied to all the trees in the forest. In further iterations number of newly generated trees will decrease because the age of all trees except the new ones will be incremented.

Age = 0	1	1	1	1
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Figure 2 : Tree before local seeding.

Figure 3 : Tree after local seeding.

Population Limiting :

Population limiting is required to avoid immeasurable growth of the forest. The parameter used to define the number of trees is called “area limit”. Area limit is defined identical to the initial number of trees in the forest [2]. Population limiting involves two steps; first, take away all the trees that have crossed their age limit, i.e., life-time, and add them to the candidate population. Next, category the trees according to their fitness values in descending order, which in our case is the classification accuracy. After sorting if the number of trees is greater than the area limit, remove the extra trees and add them to the candidate population.

Global Seeding :

Global seeding is applied on some percentage of the candidate population. This percentage is the “transfer rate” parameter. The “Global Seeding Changes (GSC)” is another predefined parameter. Global seeding is applied on selected trees and in result the value of GSC number of features of each selected tree is changed. These changes result into a new tree with age 0. This newly generated tree is added to the forest.

Updating the Best Tree :

Trees are sorted according to their fitness value or classification accuracy. The age of best tree is updated to ‘0’ so that the age limit parameter would not rule it out. As local seeding is only applied to the trees with age ‘0’, this step helps in locally optimizing the best solution that we have so far.

Stopping Conditions :

Three stop over situations can be considered like all evolutionary algorithms:

- (i) Fixed number of iterations.
- (ii) No change observed in fitness value for number of iterations.
- (iii) Required level of fitness value is achieved.

3.3 Process 3 : Ensemble-Based Classification :

Three basic classifiers are used for ensemble model of sentiment classification. Support Vector Machine (SVM) k -Nearest Neighbor (k -NN) and Naïve Bayes (NB), and Support . All these supervised machine learning classifying algorithms are used in parallel topology of multi-classifier system (ensemble). In our proposed approach, parallel classifiers will optimize the classification accuracy for the sentiment analysis task.

4. Conclusion :

The hybrid of FOA-NB and FOA- k -NN has outperformed single NB and k -NN classifiers are applied to several benchmark classification datasets. After the improved results, the proposed approach of MRmR-based feature subset selection with FOA was applied on the product review dataset taken from Amazon. For sentiment classification we have implemented three classifiers, including SVM, to observe the classification accuracy. The research was carried out on three different numbers of instances with two sizes of initial population. The increase in the size of instances gradually increases the computation time of FOA. Out of all three classifiers, SVM takes more time with FOA, whereas the computation time of k -NN and NB gradually increase with the number of instances. The sentiment classification accuracy of this dataset has improved 15-20% when the FOA-MRmR feature subset selection technique is applied. The ensemble of k -NN, NB, and SVM classifiers is implemented to optimize the final output.

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